

Electrolysis assisted acetylation of primary aromatic amines in the acetic acid using platinum electrode

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Electrolysis assisted synthesis of anilides from primary aromatic amines in the acetic acid solvent using platinum electrode have been carried out at controlled potential for the investigation of a new ecofriendly synthetic method. The reaction is an example of oxidation of amines with substitution. Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at platinum plates of dimensions 1.0 cm × 0.5 cm as working as well as counter electrode. Various parameters of the reaction with yield are reported here.

Keywords: Electrolysis assisted, platinum electrode, acetylation, controlled potential, green chemistry.

Introduction

In the present communication we are reporting the result of our studies on the electrolysis assisted acetylation of some primary aromatic amines in the acetic acid solvent using platinum electrode. The reaction is an important example of oxidation with substitution which is just different from the conventional chemical methods. Singh *et al.*¹⁻³ have studied some anodic processes in controlled potential electrolysis. The reaction is a result of oxidative substitution of amino group in primary aromatic compounds. For this purpose all the electrolysis were carried out at constant potential by using a conventional three electrode cell assembly with platinum^{4,5} working as well as counter electrodes and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. The synthetic procedure consists of acetylation of aromatic primary amines viz. *o*-anisidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-nitro aniline, aniline and naphthylamine. At definite potential the electrode surface is covered by a layer of the coloured product which is continually diffused in the bulk.

Results and discussion

It is well known that acetylation of aromatic primary amines⁶ was generally carried out by using acetic anhydride or acetyl chlorides. Acetic acid in presence or absence of zinc dust can also be used for the conversion of aniline to acetanilide. These methods require high temperature, gas trap and about 1.5 h refluxation.

Ameta and verma⁷ have reported the microwave induced acetylation of aromatic amines using acetic acid. On account of the above facts and wide applicability of microwave irradiation in chemical reaction enhancement⁸⁻¹² for the synthesis of anilides from some substituted primary aromatic amines using acetic acid in the absence of zinc dust.

Electrochemical reactions are now being used as an important tool in the field of organic synthesis. The important aspect of electroorganic synthesis is that it is carried out by using a very small amount of electricity and also without using hazardous chemicals. Electroorganic synthesis has attracted much attention owing to several advantages such as rapid reaction rates and higher yield of pure products with non-polluting nature of the reactant.

For the acetylation of primary aromatic amines in the acetic acid we propose the following mechanism (Scheme 1) which explains the each step of the reaction.

Scheme 1

In this system the reaction takes place at the room temperature in a potential range 0.80 to 2.00 V but the specific potential for the reaction from various observations is found to be approximately 1.5 V vs Hg/Hg^{2+} . During electrolysis $0.7\text{--}2.8 \text{ Fmol}^{-1}$ of electricity was passed which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods.

All the electrolysis was carried out at their corresponding oxidation potentials and was completed in 3.5 h. After three hour no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. All the products were solid, coloured and entirely different from the starting compound. The observations recorded in these reactions are depicted in Table 1.

The product was extracted from the reaction mixture to chloroform by simple solvent extraction method after diluting the reaction solution with double distilled water. Two immiscible layers of above solvent were shaken in separatory funnel and allowed to settle, after some time the chloroform layer

containing desired product was removed. Chloroform was evaporated and fine crystals of product were obtained after recrystallization.

Analysis of the product:

All the products were analyzed by chemical method as well as by spectral studies. As per mechanism following products are obtained in the electrolysis for nuclear oxidation.

Table 1. Current-potential data of electrolysis as recorded by potentiostat

Time	Current in mA				
	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	<i>p</i> -Nitro aniline	Aniline	Naphthylamine
3.5 h	25.3	7.4	9.4	6.3	19.9
	26.2	8.0	10.1	6.8	20.4
	27.5	8.6	11.2	7.2	20.8
	28.4	9.3	12.0	7.9	21.2
	29.9	9.9	12.8	8.5	21.8
	31.2	10.4	14.5	9.1	22.6
	32.6	10.9	15.8	9.9	23.2
	34.7	11.5	16.7	10.5	23.7
	37.0	11.8	18.3	11.3	24.8
	38.8	12.4	19.7	12.8	25.9
Applied potential (V)	2.00	1.50	2.00	0.80	1.50

Characterisation:

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded on a VEB Wagetechink Rapio PHMK05 instrument and were compared with standard results. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 300 FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. Chemical shifts are on parts per million (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. Microanalyses were carried out in the Elementar Vario EL III instrument. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000–400 cm⁻¹).

o-Methoxy acetanilide (**1**): Yield 65%; mol. wt. 253; m.p. 88°C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 745, 860, 935 (substituted benzene), 1655, 1695 (CO), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (=C-H Aromatic), 3425 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 2.35 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.72 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 8.16 (s, 1H, NH), 8.65 (s, 2H, Ar-H), 8.76 (s, 2H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 46.84 (OCH₃), 51.1 (NHCOCH₃), 126.8, 134.5, 136.1, 138.2, 138.3, 151.0 (6 Aromatic C), 163.2 (NHCOCH₃). Analysis Calcd. for C₉H₁₁NO₂: C, 65.45; H, 5.45; N, 8.48; O, 19.39. Found: C, 65.41; H, 5.42; N, 8.35; O, 19.22.

p-Methoxy acetanilide (**2**): Yield 51%; mol. wt. 253; m.p. 300°C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 745, 860, 935 (substituted benzene), 1655, 1695 (CO), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (=C-H Aromatic), 3425 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 2.35 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 2.72 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 8.16 (s, 2H, NH), 8.65 (s, 2H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 46.2 and 50.4 (OCH₃), 51.1 (NHCOCH₃), 126.8, 134.5, 136.1, 138.2, 138.3, 151.0 (6 Aromatic C), 163.2 (NHCOCH₃). Analysis Calcd. for C₉H₁₁NO₂: C, 65.45; H, 5.45; N, 8.48; O, 19.39. Found: C, 65.35; H, 5.38; N, 8.30; O, 19.20.

p-Nitro acetanilide (**3**): Yield 55%; mol. wt. 253; m.p. 112°C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 745, 860, 935 (substituted benzene),

1655, 1695 (CO), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (=C-H Aromatic), 3425 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 2.73 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 8.14 (s, 2H, NH), 8.65 (s, 2H, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 51.1 (NHCOCH₃), 126.8, 134.5, 136.1, 138.2, 138.3, 151.0 (6 Aromatic C), 163.2 (NHCOCH₃). Analysis Calcd. for C₈H₈N₂O₃: C, 53.33; H, 4.44; N, 15.55; O, 26.66. Found: C, 53.18; H, 4.41; N, 15.28; O, 26.43.

Acetanilide (**4**): Yield 74%; mol. wt. 185; m.p. 110°C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 735, 860, 910 (substituted benzene), 1608 (C=C Aromatic), 1681 (CO), 2830 (C-H), 3035 (=C-H Aromatic), 3428 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 2.72 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 7.25–7.69 (m, 5H, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.15 (s, 1H, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 50.8 (NHCOCH₃), 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 125.7 (6 Aromatic C), 163.0 (NHCOCH₃). Analysis Calcd. for C₈H₉NO: C, 71.11; H, 6.67; N, 10.37; O, 11.85. Found: C, 70.86; H, 6.62; N, 10.25; O, 11.67.

N-Acetyl naphthylamine (**5**): Yield 58%; mol. wt. 185; m.p. 160°C; IR ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 735, 860, 910 (substituted benzene), 1608 (C=C Aromatic), 1681 (CO), 2830 (C-H), 3035 (=C-H Aromatic), 3428 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 2.72 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 7.25–7.69 (m, 7H, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.15 (s, 1H, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS): δ 50.8 (NHCOCH₃), 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 125.7, 128.5, 129.5, 135.1 (10 Aromatic C), 163.0 (NHCOCH₃). Analysis Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁NO: C, 77.83; H, 5.94; N, 7.56. Found: C, 77.43; H, 5.62; N, 7.36.

Experimental

Reaction mixture: The reaction mixture contains the 50 mL of 0.01 mol solution of starting material using acetic acid as a solvent and 25 mL of the 0.1 mol aqueous solution of KCl, which is used as supporting electrolyte^{13–15}. In this reaction acetic acid works as a solvent as well as nucleophile for the substitution.

Reagents: All the compounds *o*-anisidine, *p*-anisidine, *p*-nitroaniline, aniline, naphthylamine, acetic acid KCl and chloroform were of AnalaR grade. Water used was double distilled.

Electrolysis: The controlled potential electrolysis were performed at room temperature in conventional three electrode cell assembly containing platinum^{16,17} (flattened sheet of dimension 1.0 cm × 0.5 cm) as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as refer-

ence electrode. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. The current potential data was recorded with the help of potentiostat.

Conclusion

It is obvious from the studies that the electrolysis assisted acetylation as a oxidative acetylation of aromatic compounds provides a good method for the aromatic acetylation which is not so easy by chemical method. The method does not require any special condition to maintain the reaction temperature since the electrolysis was carried out at room temperature. Therefore the method is simple, ecofriendly and a part of green chemistry. The unique feature of this reaction is that acetic acid works as a solvent as well as nucleophile for the substitution.

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